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TIMES FOR CARRYING OUT AGROTECHNICAL MEASURES TO INCREASE THE YIELD OF ATROPA BELLADONNA L.

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***Abstract.** Currently, the concept of integrating modern medicine and traditional medicine is being popularized in a number of countries, and it is believed that integrative medicine may be the medicine of the future. To solve such an urgent problem, measures are being taken to effectively use the vast undeveloped lands in our country. It is especially necessary to properly implement agrotechnical measures in the cultivation and increase of the wild medicinal plant *Atropa belladonna* l.*

***Keywords:** *Atropa belladonna* l, Renal, Hyoscyamine, Alkaloid, stratification, combing, vegetative.*

СРОКИ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ АГРОТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ПО ПОВЫШЕНИЮ УРОЖАЙНОСТИ АТРОПА BELLADONNA L.

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***Аннотация.** В настоящее время в ряде стран набирает популярность концепция интеграции современной медицины и народной медицины, и предполагается, что интегративная медицина может стать медициной*

*будущего. Для решения столь актуальной проблемы принимаются меры по эффективному использованию крупных неосвоенных земель в нашей стране. Лекарственная белладонна, произрастающая особенно в диком виде, *Atropa belladonna* L. Необходимо правильно проводить агротехнические мероприятия при выращивании растений и повышать их продуктивность.*

Ключевые слова: *Atropa belladonna* L, Почечный, Хьюциамин, Алкалоид, крахмала образование, шунтирующий, вегетативный.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that more than 50% of the medicines produced by pharmaceutical enterprises worldwide are made from medicinal plant raw materials. The rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry in most countries, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, has led to a sharp increase in the demand for medicinal plant raw materials by such enterprises. It should be noted that due to the limited reserves of naturally growing medicinal plants, the demand for medicinal plant raw materials by pharmaceutical enterprises can be met mainly only by growing medicinal plants.

In order to organize the cultural cultivation and processing of medicinal plants, support the establishment of plantations of medicinal plants, as well as the widespread use of medicinal plants in the prevention and treatment of diseases, 1 Resolution No. PQ-251 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev was adopted on May 20, 2022. Over the years, the republic has been implementing consistent reforms in the field of medicinal plant protection, rational use of natural resources, and the establishment of plantations where medicinal plants are grown and their processing. Therefore, providing the pharmaceutical industry with high-quality, abundant, affordable and ecologically clean raw materials remains a major challenge. This situation, of course, requires providing farms engaged in the cultivation of medicinal plant raw materials with specialists who are well versed in the technologies of growing medicinal plants.

MAIN PART

Common (medicinal) belladonna - *Atropa belladonna* L. Caucasian belladonna *Atropa caucasica* Kreyer; relatives - belongs to the Solanaceae family. Belladonna preparations are used as antispasmodics in various spasmodic cases (intestinal and urinary tract spasms) and as painkillers in gastric and duodenal ulcers, cholecystitis, gallstone disease, renal colic, as well as in the treatment of bronchial asthma and to reduce the fluid secreted by the salivary and mucous glands. In addition, it is also used to dilate the pupils in eye diseases. A root preparation is given to treat Parkinson's disease. Atropine and scopolamine are used in medicine from the belladonna plant, while hyoscyamine is not used because it is more toxic.

The land where belladonna is planted should be thoroughly studied. It is a perennial herb that can reach 2 meters in height. The plant is mainly grown in the Krasnodar Territory, Poltava and Voronezh regions. Currently, it is also being planted in Uzbekistan. It is advisable to plow the land taking into account the mechanical composition of the soil, the level of salinity and fertility. If the land is plowed properly, it will be possible for the plant's roots to develop well. Before planting belladonna, in the fall, 20-30 tons of organic fertilizer and superphosphate fertilizer are applied at a rate of 70% of the annual rate, and in areas with deep water, 20 kg of nitrogen fertilizer is applied and plowed to a depth of 25-30 cm. Belladonna can be planted in the fall or early spring.

It is a thermophilic plant with a long growing season. In early spring, the land is leveled, weeds are removed and the soil temperature is 20-22°C. Since the seeds of the plant are hard, they are stratified for 2 months before planting. 8 kg of seeds are used per hectare. The seeds are sown at a depth of 1.5-2 cm, and the row spacing is 60 cm.

Since the seeds of the plant are hard, they germinate in 15-17 days. Belladonna is considered resistant to weeds, pests and heat. During the growth and development period, belladonna must be protected from weeds and pests 2-3 times. Caring for the plant during the growing season is no different from that of arable crops. Feeding belladonna should begin with 30 kg of nitrogen and 25 kg of potassium fertilizer per hectare before the budding phase. Its development is much faster. When the plant reaches the flowering phase, it is fed a second time with 40 kg of nitrogen and the remaining phosphorus fertilizer per hectare.

Since belladonna is a heat-resistant and cool-loving plant, it is necessary to water after fertilization. If watering is not carried out on time, its leaves may become small and of poor quality. Because its leaves, grass and roots are used in medicine. It is recommended to water the plant 8-9 times during the season.

In the first year, 125-130 days pass from the moment the plant sprouts to the moment the seeds ripen. In the first year, the leaves of belladonna are harvested by hand twice. Starting from the second year, its harvest can be harvested 4-5 times. The vegetation period lasts until the cold weather sets in. In the second year, the leaves are harvested first, then the grass is harvested. The third time, the leaves are harvested, and in the fall, the grass is harvested. When using this method, it is possible to harvest more of it. Its leaves should always be harvested before flowering. The collected leaves are dried quickly. Since the dried leaves are hygroscopic, they are carefully stacked and stored in dry bags without absorbing moisture.

If agrotechnical measures are carried out at a high level, and weeds and pests are combated in a timely manner, 15-18 centners of dry leaves can be produced per hectare of belladonna planting area.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, before planting *Atropa belladonna* L., in the fall, 20-30 tons of organic fertilizer and superphosphate fertilizer are applied at a rate of 70% of the annual norm, and in areas with deep water, 20 kg of nitrogen fertilizer is applied and plowed to a depth of 25-30 cm. Belladonna can be planted in the fall or early spring. It is a thermophilic plant with a long growing season. In early spring, the land is leveled, weeds are dug up, and the soil temperature is 20-22 ° C. Since the seeds of the plant are hard, they are stratified for 2 months before planting. 8 kg of seeds are used per hectare. When the seed depth is 1.5-2 cm and the row spacing is 60 cm, its fertility and medicinal properties are preserved very well. If agrotechnical measures for *Atropa belladonna* L. are carried out in this order, 15-18 centners of dry leaves can be produced per hectare of planted area.

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